

NOTE ON A DETERMINANT

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Received: 6/13/19, Accepted: 6/10/20, Published: 6/18/20

Abstract

In this paper, we give the value of some determinants in terms of the p -relative class number where p is a prime number such that $p \equiv 3 \pmod 4$.

1. Introduction

Let p be an odd prime number, \mathbb{F}_p be the field of p elements, $\zeta = e^{\frac{2i\pi}{p}}$ and g be a primitive element of \mathbb{F}_p^\times . The extension $\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}$ is a Galois extension. Let $\sigma \in \text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q})$ defined by $\zeta^\sigma = \zeta^{g^2}$. Recall that $\text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}) \simeq \mathbb{F}_p^\times$. In this paper, for $a \in \mathbb{F}_p^\times$ and $b \in \mathbb{Q}$, we denote by $\mathcal{D}_g(p, a, b)$ the circulant determinant whose first line is given by

$$\frac{1}{b - \zeta^a} - \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{-a}} \quad \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{a\sigma}} - \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{-a\sigma}} \cdots \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{a\sigma^{\frac{p-3}{2}}}} - \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{-a\sigma^{\frac{p-3}{2}}}}.$$

In this paper, we prove the following theorem.

Theorem 1. *We have the following properties:*

1. *We have $\mathcal{D}_g(p, a, b) = 0$ if $p \equiv 1 \pmod 4$.*
2. *Suppose $p \equiv 3 \pmod 4$. The determinant $\mathcal{D}_g(p, a, b)$ does not depend on the choice of the value of g : consequently, it will be denoted in the following by $\mathcal{D}(p, a, b)$. There exists $d(p, a, b) \in \mathbb{Q}$ such that $\mathcal{D}(p, a, b) = d(p, a, b) \sqrt{-p}$. Furthermore,*

$$d(p, a, 1) = (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \times 2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \times p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} \times h_p^- \times \left(\frac{a}{p}\right),$$

where h_p^- is the p -th relative class number.

Remark 1. The case $b = -1$ is technically more involved and will be the aim of another paper.

For example, for $p = 7$, $a = b = 1$ and $5 \pmod 7$ being a primitive element of \mathbb{F}_7^\times , $\mathcal{D}(7, 1, 1)$ is defined by

$$\mathcal{D}(7, 1, 1) = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{1}{1-\zeta} - \frac{1}{1-\bar{\zeta}} & \frac{1}{1-\zeta^4} - \frac{1}{1-\bar{\zeta}^4} & \frac{1}{1-\zeta^2} - \frac{1}{1-\bar{\zeta}^2} \\ \frac{1}{1-\zeta^2} - \frac{1}{1-\bar{\zeta}^2} & \frac{1}{1-\zeta} - \frac{1}{1-\bar{\zeta}} & \frac{1}{1-\zeta^4} - \frac{1}{1-\bar{\zeta}^4} \\ \frac{1}{1-\zeta^4} - \frac{1}{1-\bar{\zeta}^4} & \frac{1}{1-\zeta^2} - \frac{1}{1-\bar{\zeta}^2} & \frac{1}{1-\zeta} - \frac{1}{1-\bar{\zeta}} \end{vmatrix}.$$

By Theorem 1, this determinant is given by

$$\mathcal{D}(7, 1, 1) = (-1)^{\frac{7-3}{4}} \times 2^{\frac{7-3}{2}} \times 7^{\frac{7-7}{4}} \times h_7^- \times \left(\frac{1}{7}\right) \times \sqrt{-7} = -4\sqrt{-7}.$$

Using Theorem 1, we deduce this beautiful corollary.

Corollary 1. *Suppose $p > 3$ and $p \equiv 3 \pmod 4$. Let $\mathcal{C}(p, a)$ be the circulant determinant whose first line is given by*

$$\frac{1}{1-\zeta^a} \quad \frac{1}{1-\zeta^{a\sigma}} \cdots \frac{1}{1-\zeta^{a\sigma^{\frac{p-3}{2}}}}$$

and $h(-p)$ be the class number of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-p})$. We have the following result:

$$\mathcal{C}(p, a) = (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} h_p^- \left(\frac{p-1}{4h(-p)} + \left(\frac{a}{p}\right) \frac{\sqrt{-p}}{2} \right). \tag{1}$$

In 1851, Kummer (see [3], p.473) conjectured that $h_p^- \sim 2p \left(\frac{p}{4\pi^2}\right)^{\frac{p-1}{4}} = G(p)$ as $p \rightarrow +\infty$. For all rational integers ν such that $0 \leq \nu \leq \frac{p-3}{2}$, denote by g_ν the rational integer such that $1 \leq g_\nu < p$, $g_\nu \equiv g^{2\nu} \pmod p$ (particularly, $g_0 = 1$). Denote by \mathcal{T}_p the circulant determinant whose first line is given by

$$\frac{1}{\tan\left(\frac{\pi}{p}\right)} \quad \frac{1}{\tan\left(\frac{\pi}{p}g_1\right)} \cdots \frac{1}{\tan\left(\frac{\pi}{p}g_{\frac{p-3}{2}}\right)}.$$

From Theorem 1, we deduce the following result.

Corollary 2. *Denote by $(p_j)_{j \geq 1}$ the sequence of prime numbers p such that $p \equiv 3 \pmod 4$ (so that $p_1 = 3$, $p_2 = 7$ and so on). Kummer's conjecture is true for this set of prime numbers if and only if $\mathcal{T}_{p_j} \sim \left(\frac{p_j}{\pi}\right)^{\frac{p_j-1}{2}}$ as $j \rightarrow +\infty$.*

2. Two Useful Lemmas

Lemma 1. *Let $x \in \mathbb{F}_p^\times$. We have*

$$\sum_{j=1}^{p-1} j\zeta^{jx} = -\frac{p}{1-\zeta^x}.$$

Proof. Let Φ_p be the p -th cyclotomic polynomial. We have

$$\sum_{j=1}^{p-1} j\zeta^{jx} = \zeta^x \Phi'_p(\zeta^x) = \frac{p}{\zeta^x - 1}.$$

□

Lemma 2. Let $\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}$ be a non trivial character and $\mathcal{S}(\chi)$ be the sum defined by

$$\mathcal{S}(\chi) = \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \frac{\chi(x)}{1 - \zeta^x}.$$

We have

$$\mathcal{S}(\chi) = -B_{1,\bar{\chi}} \times \tau(\chi),$$

where $B_{1,\bar{\chi}}$ is a generalized Bernoulli number (see [5]) and $\tau(\chi)$ is a Gauss sum defined by

$$\tau(\chi) = \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \chi(x)\zeta^x.$$

Proof. Using Lemma 1, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} -p\mathcal{S}(\chi) &= \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \chi(x) \frac{-p}{1 - \zeta^x} = \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \chi(x) \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} j\zeta^{jx} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} j \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \chi(x)\zeta^{jx} = \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} j\overline{\chi(j)} \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \chi(jx)\zeta^{jx} \\ &= p \left(\frac{1}{p} \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} j\overline{\chi(j)} \right) \times \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \chi(x)\zeta^x = pB_{1,\bar{\chi}} \times \tau(\chi). \end{aligned}$$

□

3. Proof of the First Part of the Theorem

Suppose $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. Let ξ be a $\frac{p-1}{2}$ -th root of unity and $Z_{b,a} = \frac{1}{b-\zeta^a} - \frac{1}{b-\zeta^{-a}}$. Consider the polynomial

$$P_{b,a}(X) = \sum_{l=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} Z_{b,a}^{\sigma^l} X^l \in \mathbb{Q}(\zeta)[X].$$

$\mathcal{D}_g(p, a, b)$ being a circulant determinant, by a well known result, we have

$$\mathcal{D}_g(p, a, b) = \prod_{k=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} P_{b,a}(\zeta^k). \tag{2}$$

Let \mathcal{C} be the set of squares modulo p . Since $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, we have $-1 \in \mathcal{C}$ so that

$$\begin{aligned} P_{b,a}(1) &= \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{ac}} - \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{-ac}} = \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{ac}} - \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \frac{1}{b - \zeta^{ac}} \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

This proves that $\mathcal{D}_g(p, a, b) = 0$ for $p \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$. □

4. Proof of the Second Part of the Theorem

Suppose $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$. Denote by $\widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-$ (respectively $\widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^+$) the set of odd characters (respectively even characters) of \mathbb{F}_p^\times . From equality (2)

$$\mathcal{D}_g(p, a, b) = \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} \sum_{x=1}^{p-1} \frac{\chi(x)}{b - \zeta^{ax}},$$

which proves that $\mathcal{D}_g(p, a, b)$ does not depend on the choice of the value of g .

Recall that $\sigma \in G$ is defined by $\zeta^\sigma = \zeta^{g^2}$. Let j be the complex conjugation. It is not difficult to see that $\mathcal{D}(p, a, b)^\sigma = \mathcal{D}(p, a, b)$ and $\mathcal{D}(p, a, b)^j = -\mathcal{D}(p, a, b)$. By a well known fact, as $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, the field $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-p})$ is a subfield of $\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)$ and the extension $\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-p})$ is a cyclic extension whose Galois group is generated by σ . As $\mathcal{D}(p, a, b)^\sigma = \mathcal{D}(p, a, b)$, $\mathcal{D}(p, a, b)$ is fixed by every automorphism in $\text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-p}))$. By Galois theory, $\mathcal{D}(p, a, b)$ is an element of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-p})$. In other words, there exists $d(p, a, b) \in \mathbb{Q}$ and $e(p, a, b) \in \mathbb{Q}$ such that

$$\mathcal{D}(p, a, b) = e(p, a, b) + d(p, a, b)\sqrt{-p}.$$

But $\mathcal{D}(p, a, b)^j = -\mathcal{D}(p, a, b)$ so that $e(p, a, b) = 0$. Finally,

$$\mathcal{D}(p, a, b) = d(p, a, b)\sqrt{-p}.$$

Show that

$$d(p, 1, 1) = (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \times 2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \times p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} \times h_p^-.$$

From equality (2) and Lemma 2, we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}(p, 1, 1) &= \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} \mathcal{S}(\chi) = \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} -B_{1, \bar{\chi}} \tau(\chi) = 2^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} -\frac{1}{2} B_{1, \bar{\chi}} \tau(\chi) \\ &= 2^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} \tau(\chi) \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} -\frac{1}{2} B_{1, \chi}. \end{aligned}$$

By Corollary 4.6 of [5] or Theorem 11.7.16 of [1],

$$\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} \tau(\chi) = (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} p^{\frac{p-2}{2}} \sqrt{-1}, \quad \prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^+} \tau(\chi) = p^{\frac{p-3}{4}},$$

so that

$$\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} \tau(\chi) = \frac{(-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} p^{\frac{p-2}{2}} \sqrt{-1}}{p^{\frac{p-3}{4}}} = (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \sqrt{-1} p^{\frac{p-1}{4}}. \tag{3}$$

By Theorem 4.17 of [5],

$$\prod_{\chi \in \widehat{\mathbb{F}_p^\times}^-} -\frac{1}{2} B_{1, \chi} = \frac{h_p^-}{2p}. \tag{4}$$

From (3) and (4), we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}(p, 1, 1) &= 2^{\frac{p-1}{2}} (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} \sqrt{-1} p^{\frac{p-1}{4}} \frac{h_p^-}{2p} \\ &= (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} 2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} h_p^- \sqrt{-p}. \end{aligned}$$

Let $a \in \mathbb{F}_p^\times$ be a square modulo p . As $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$, to terminate the proof of the theorem, it suffices to prove that

$$\mathcal{D}(p, a, 1) = \mathcal{D}(p, 1, 1), \quad \mathcal{D}(p, -a, 1) = -\mathcal{D}(p, 1, 1).$$

Let $\tau \in \text{Gal}(\mathbb{Q}(\zeta)/\mathbb{Q})$ defined by $\zeta^\tau = \zeta^a$. We have $\mathcal{D}(p, a, 1) = \mathcal{D}(p, 1, 1)^\tau$ with $\mathcal{D}(p, 1, 1) \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-p})$ so that

$$\mathcal{D}(p, a, 1) = \mathcal{D}(p, 1, 1).$$

We have $\mathcal{D}(p, -a, 1) = \mathcal{D}(p, -1, 1)^\tau$ with $\mathcal{D}(p, -1, 1) \in \mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-p})$ so that

$$\mathcal{D}(p, -a, 1) = \mathcal{D}(p, -1, 1).$$

We obtain, j being the complex conjugation

$$\mathcal{D}(p, -a, 1) = \mathcal{D}(p, -1, 1) = \mathcal{D}(p, 1, 1)^j = (-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \mathcal{D}(p, 1, 1).$$

As $p \equiv 3 \pmod 4$, $\frac{p-1}{2}$ is an odd integer, so that

$$\mathcal{D}(p, -a, 1) = -\mathcal{D}(p, 1, 1).$$

The theorem is proved. □

5. Proof of Corollary 1

To prove (1), it is sufficient to prove that

$$\mathcal{C}(p, 1) = (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} h_p^- \left(\frac{p-1}{4h(-p)} + \frac{\sqrt{-p}}{2} \right).$$

Consider the polynomial

$$Q(X) = \sum_{l=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \frac{1}{1-\zeta^{\sigma^l}} X^l \in \mathbb{Q}(\zeta)[X].$$

Since $\mathcal{C}(p, 1)$ is a circulant determinant

$$\mathcal{C}(p, 1) = \prod_{k=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} Q(\xi^k).$$

Let k be a rational integer such that $0 < k \leq \frac{p-3}{2}$. The equality $\sum_{l=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \xi^{kl} = 0$ implies $Q(\xi^k) = \frac{1}{2} P_{1,1}(\xi^k)$, so that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(p, 1) &= \frac{Q(1)}{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} P_{1,1}(1)} \prod_{k=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} P_{1,1}(\xi^k) = \frac{Q(1)}{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} P_{1,1}(1)} \mathcal{D}(p, 1, 1) \\ &= \frac{Q(1)}{2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} P_{1,1}(1)} \times (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} 2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} h_p^- \sqrt{-p} \\ &= (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} h_p^- \frac{Q(1)}{P_{1,1}(1)} \sqrt{-p}. \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 2, $P_{1,1}(1) = -B_{1,(\frac{p}{p})} \times \tau\left(\left(\frac{p}{p}\right)\right)$ which implies that $P_{1,1}(1) = h(-p)\sqrt{-p}$ by Theorem 4.17 of [5] and Theorem 11.7.16 of [1]. Furthermore, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 2Q(1) &= P_{1,1}(1) + \sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{1}{1-\zeta^k} = P_{1,1}(1) + \frac{\Phi'_p(1)}{\Phi_p(1)} \\ &= P_{1,1}(1) + \frac{p(p-1)}{2p} = \frac{p-1}{2} + h(-p)\sqrt{-p}, \end{aligned}$$

so that $Q(1) = \frac{p-1}{4} + \frac{h(-p)\sqrt{-p}}{2}$. Finally,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(p, 1) &= (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} h_p^- \frac{\frac{p-1}{4} + \frac{h(-p)\sqrt{-p}}{2}}{h(-p)\sqrt{-p}} \sqrt{-p} \\ &= (-1)^{\frac{p-3}{4}} p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} h_p^- \left(\frac{p-1}{4h(-p)} + \frac{\sqrt{-p}}{2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

which concludes the proof. □

6. Proof of Corollary 2

We can easily see that $\mathcal{D}(p_j, 1, 1) = (-1)^{\frac{p_j-3}{4}} \sqrt{-1} \mathcal{T}_{p_j}$, so that, by Theorem 1,

$$\mathcal{T}_{p_j} = 2^{\frac{p_j-3}{2}} p_j^{\frac{p_j-7}{4}} h_{p_j}^- \sqrt{p_j} = \frac{h_{p_j}^-}{G(p_j)} \left(\frac{p_j}{\pi} \right)^{\frac{p_j-1}{2}},$$

which concludes the proof. □

Remark 2. Let $p \equiv 3 \pmod{4}$ be a prime number. By Hadamard’s inequality,

$$\mathcal{T}_p \leq \left(\sum_{\nu=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \frac{1}{\tan^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{p} g_\nu \right)} \right)^{\frac{p-1}{4}}, \tag{5}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\nu=0}^{\frac{p-3}{2}} \frac{1}{\tan^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{p} g_\nu \right)} &= \sum_{g_\nu < \frac{p}{2}} \frac{1}{\tan^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{p} g_\nu \right)} + \sum_{g_\nu > \frac{p}{2}} \frac{1}{\tan^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{p} g_\nu \right)} \\ &= \sum_{g_\nu < \frac{p}{2}} \frac{1}{\tan^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{p} g_\nu \right)} + \sum_{g_\nu > \frac{p}{2}} \frac{1}{\tan^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{p} (p - g_\nu) \right)} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{1}{\tan^2 \left(\frac{k\pi}{p} \right)} = \frac{(p-1)(p-2)}{6} \quad (\text{see [4]}). \end{aligned}$$

Using (5) and Corollary 2, we obtain $2^{\frac{p-3}{2}} p^{\frac{p-7}{4}} h_p^- \sqrt{p} < \left(\frac{p^2}{6} \right)^{\frac{p-1}{4}}$, so that $h_p^- < 2p \left(\frac{p}{24} \right)^{\frac{p-1}{4}}$. Using much more sophisticated methods from analytic number theory, it has been proved in [2], that $h_p^- \leq 2p \left(\frac{p}{39} \right)^{\frac{p-1}{4}}$ if $p > 9649$.

Acknowledgments I thank the referee for helpful suggestions.

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